

**ON THE ISSUE OF EDITING AND EDITORIAL WORKS IN THE SCIENTIFIC
RESEARCH OF A.URINBOEV****Burkhanov Ilyoskhon Mukhiddinovich,**

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Abstract: The article emphasizes the effectiveness of the editorial work carried out by Asomiddin Urinbaev, The great contribution made in preparing for publication many works such as Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far Narshahi's "History of Bukhara" and Fasih Khawafi's "Mujmal-i Fasihhi" is briefly analyzed.

Key words: Editing, collection, editing, spelling, author.

The editorial work on preparing the collection of scientific conferences for publication, carried out by Asomiddin Urinbayev, was one of the most difficult operations. Because articles in Uzbek, Russian, and English were accepted for this scientific conference, each author prepared an article using his own style and scientific field. The editor edited these articles without changing the content, corrected spelling errors (if necessary), and took into account shortcomings and achievements. In particular, he played a key role in preparing the collection for publication at the international conference on "Amir Temur and his place in world history" and prepared all the theses in the collection for publication.

The practical experience of the scientist in the preparation of books for publication and editing was analyzed one by one, as the data was different:

-In 1965, he prepared for publication a book in Russian titled "Manuscript sources of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR on the history of Central Asia during the period of its annexation to Russia (Bukhara)", researched by L.M. Epifanova.

-In 1966, he edited and prepared for publication the book "History of Bukhara" by Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far Narshahi, translated from Persian into Uzbek by A. Rasulov. The 1991 and 1993 editions of this book were edited by Asomiddin Orinboev.

-In 1980, he served as the editor-in-chief of Fasih Khawafi's "Mujmal-i Fasikhi" (in Russian), translated by D. Yusupova.

- In 1991, he edited and prepared for publication, as the editor-in-chief, Muhammad Rafi

Ansari's work "Dastur ul-muluk", translated by A. Vildanova.

- In 1991, Asomiddin Orinboev was responsible for the publication of the book "Navoiy dastkhati" prepared by S. Ganieva, a Navoi scholar.

-In 1991, he served as the editor-in-chief of the publication of Abu Sai Gardizi's "Zayn al-Akhbar", translated from Persian by A.K. Arends.

-Edited and prepared for publication the book "History of Amir Temur" by Ibn Arabshah, translated from Arabic into Uzbek by U. Uvatov. This research consists of two books, both of which were published under the editorship of Asomiddin Urinbayev.

-Edited and edited the book "The Ancestors of Amir Temur. (Selections - Translation from Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnoma"), published in 1992, as the responsible editor.

- Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's book "Zafarnoma. Events of Movarunnahr, 1360-1370" was also edited by Asomiddin Orinboev.

- Worked as an editorial board in preparation for publication of the book "The creativity of the Timurids in the sources of the period"

- He made a great contribution to the preparation of the book "Manuscripts Written in Khorezm" by G. Masharipova, published in 1997.

- Edited and did other work for the publication of the study "Central Asia in the written sources of the Timurid period (historical-geographical plates)" authored by O. Boriev.

-He served as the editor-in-chief of the publication of the work "Jaloliddin Manguberdi", published in 1999.

- Asomiddin Urinbayev participated in the editorial board and scientific editor of the illustrated book "Jaloliddin Manguberdi", published in Uzbek, Russian, and English in 1999.

- In 2001, he served as the editor-in-chief of the book "Oriental Miniatures", published in English. This book contains a collection of miniatures from manuscript sources on the history of the 14th-17th centuries, kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- In 2003, a continuation of the above book, namely the collection of miniatures from manuscript sources on the history of the 18th-19th centuries, "Eastern Miniatures", was published. Asomiddin Urinboev, as the responsible editor, edited all

the information in the book.

- In 2008, Abdurazzak Samarkandy's work "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bahairyn" was published. This work was translated by Asomiddin Urinbaev, who also served as the editor-in-chief. This work is large in size and is one of the "masterpieces" of Asomiddin Urinbaev's scientific research, and its translation of Volume II, the second and third parts, that is, the events of 1429-1470, exceeds eight hundred pages. The editorial work in preparing this book for publication was also carried out by Asomiddin Urinbaev.

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